

Bending analysis of antisymmetric angle-ply laminates using HSDTs and the radial point interpolation method – Part II: numerical examples

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Abstract

This work makes use of the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM) and five different High-Order Shear Deformation Theories (HSDTs), to analyse several antisymmetric angle-ply composite laminated plates. The RPIM's formulation and the computer implementation of those HSDTs within the RPIM's code was properly explained in the first part of this work. In this second part, the obtained meshless solutions are compared with the available analytical solutions. In the end, the accuracy and robustness of the meshless approach are proved, making the RPIM a strong alternative to the FEM. The meshless solutions presented in this paper enhance the state-of-the-art concerning the bending analysis of antisymmetric angle-ply laminates. Additionally, this paper provides new reference solutions for maximum displacements and stresses computed with HSDTs, which is a topic with an insufficient amount of literature solutions.

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1. Introduction

Several meshless methods have been used to study the behavior of composite laminates. Nevertheless, most of the studies found in the literature combine meshless methods with simpler plate models such as the Classical Plate Theory (CLPT) and the First-Order Shear Deformation Theory (FSDT). For instance, the Element Free Galerkin Method (EFGM) was used for the bending analysis of thin plates using the CLPT [1] and also for the linear and nonlinear analysis of isotropic plates and laminates using the FSDT [2], [3]. The Reproducing Kernel Particle Method (RKPM) was the numerical tool used in the static analysis of deformable beams and plates by B. M. Donning and W. K. Liu [4], using the FSDT. Recently, Belinha et al. analyzed the bending behavior of composite laminate plates using the FSDT [5], [6] and several meshless methods (the EFGM, the RPIM, the Natural Neighbor Radial Point Interpolation Method – NNRPIM, and the Natural Radial Element Method – NREM). Making use of a global meshless approach using radial basis functions (RBFs), Ferreira et al. considered the FSDT [7] for the bending analysis of composite laminates. The FSDT was also considered in the work by Rodrigues et al. [8]. Meshless methods have also been combined with plate models with higher order. The Third-Order Shear Deformation Theory (TSDT) of Reddy [9], for instance, was combined with the EFGM [10], the global meshless approach using RBFs by Ferreira et al. [11] [12] [13] and the NNRPIM [14]; the previously cited NNRPIM (a 'truly' meshless version of the RPIM employed in this work) was also used to analyze the bending behavior of symmetric and antisymmetric laminates using distinct High-Order Shear Deformation Theories (HSDTs) [15]–[17]; Xiang et al. [18], using a meshless local radial point collocation method based on multiquadric radial basis function (MQ-RBF), analyzed the static response of isotropic, sandwich and laminated plates considering several HSDTs (by Levinson [19], Aydogdu [20], Karama [21] and Touratier [22]); a higher order shear and normal deformable plate theory (HOSNDPT) [23] [24] [25] was combined with Meshless Local Petrov-Galerkin Method (MLPG) for the analysis of thick laminated composite and functionally graded plates, etc; Tornabene et al. [26] studied doubly-curved laminated

composite shells and panels using RBFs and HSDTs based on the Carrera Unified Formulation (CUF) [27]. Shukla et al. used eight layered symmetric and antisymmetric laminated plates to perform free vibration analysis [28] considering an HSDT following a new transverse shear stress function by Kumar et al. [29] and employing an RBF based meshless approach. The same authors also performed buckling [30] and bending [31] analyses.

The RPIM has been used in the static [5], [32] and dynamic [33]–[35] analysis of composite plates and shells, the inelastic analysis of 2D solids [36], 3D contact problems [37], crack growth modelling in elastic solids [38], non-local constitutive damage models [39], etc. However, it has not yet been used for the analysis of bending antisymmetric angle-ply laminates using HSDTs – this work proposes the extension of the RPIM to that field of application. Thus, this study presents, in novelty, RPIM’s solutions for the bending of composite laminates with angle-ply layers, providing new numerical solutions for a solid mechanic’s field where the literature lacks, enhancing the state-of-the-art concerning angle-ply laminated plates, HSDTs, and the RPIM itself.

In the following sections, the authors present the obtained numerical solutions.

2. Meshless Solutions

Several antisymmetric angle-ply laminates are investigated in this section. The considered material properties are as follows:

Material 1: $E_1 = 40$ GPa, $E_2 = 1$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.25$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 0.6$ GPa and $G_{23} = 0.5$ GPa .

Material 2: $E_1 = 25$ GPa, $E_2 = 1$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.25$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 0.5$ GPa and $G_{23} = 0.2$ GPa

Uniformly distributed loads (UDL) and sinusoidal distributed transverse loads (SSL) are considered in this study, being the load functions, $q(x, y)$, presented in Eq. (1) - q_0 is the nominal load.

$$\begin{aligned} q(x, y) &= q_0 \\ q(x, y) &= q_0 \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi y}{b}\right) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where a and b are the in-plane dimensions of the plate. All the solutions found are normalized according to the following expressions and are obtained at the coordinates (x, y, z) suggested below,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w} &= w(0, 0, z) \cdot \frac{E_2 h^3}{q_0 \cdot a^4} & \bar{\sigma}_{xx} &= \sigma_{xx}(0, 0, z) \cdot \frac{h^2}{q_0 \cdot a^2} & \bar{\sigma}_{yy} &= \sigma_{yy}(0, 0, z) \cdot \frac{h^2}{q_0 \cdot a^2} \\ \bar{\tau}_{xy} &= \tau_{xy}\left(-\frac{a}{2}, -\frac{b}{2}, z\right) \cdot \frac{h}{q_0 \cdot a} & \bar{\tau}_{yz} &= \tau_{yz}\left(0, -\frac{b}{2}, z\right) \cdot \frac{h}{q_0 \cdot a} & \bar{\tau}_{xz} &= \tau_{xz}\left(\frac{a}{2}, 0, z\right) \cdot \frac{h}{q_0 \cdot a} \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

the Z -coordinates are presented in Table 1:

	$\bar{w}$	$\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$	$\bar{\sigma}_{yy}$	$\bar{\tau}_{xy}$	$\bar{\tau}_{yz}$	$\bar{\tau}_{xz}$
$(\theta / -\theta)_n$	0	$h/2$ ($k = 2n$)	$h/2$ ($k = 2n$)	$-h/2$ ($k = 1$)	0 ($k = 2$)	0 ($k = 1$)

Table 1 – Values for the z-coordinate in the places where the central transverse displacement and maximum stresses are calculated, as well as the respective index of the layer.

Regarding the formulation of the RPIM, a null polynomial basis is considered in the determination of the interpolation functions and the ‘influence-domains’ have a fixed number of nodes: 16.

2.1. Convergence Study

Before obtaining the main solutions, a suitable nodal mesh needs to be found. Thus, central transverse displacements and maximum stresses were obtained using regular nodal meshes with a progressively higher number of nodes. The nodal meshes followed a quadratic nodal distribution: $(2+1) \times (2+1)$, $(4+1) \times (4+1)$, $(8+1) \times (8+1)$, $(16+1) \times (16+1)$, $(32+1) \times (32+1)$. Due to the computer processor's limitation, the densest analysed nodal mesh has $(50+1) \times (50+1)$, corresponding to 2601 nodes.

In Erro! A origem da referência não foi encontrada. Fig. 1 is shown the graphs of the convergence studies performed on antisymmetric angle-ply laminates with stacking sequences $(30/-30)$ and $(45/-45)_3$, using two different thicknesses and the material properties of Material 1. Thus, through these convergence studies, different aspect ratios, HSDTs and stacking sequences are investigated to prove the robustness of the RPIM.

Fig. 1 – Convergence studies of the nodimensionalized central transverse displacements, maximum normalized normal stress, $\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$, and maximum normalized shear stress, $\bar{\tau}_{xz}$, computed for: (a) an antisymmetric angle-ply square laminated plate $(30/-30)$ with $a/h=4$, subjected to a sinusoidal load (SSL); (b) an antisymmetric angle-ply square laminated plate $(45/-45)_3$ with $a/h=100$, subjected to a sinusoidal load (SSL).

By analysing **Erro! A origem da referência não foi encontrada.** Fig. 1, it can be concluded that the convergence rate of the central displacement depends on the HSDT, the thickness of the plate, and the number of layers. Nevertheless, for both laminates, faster convergences are observed. Additionally, the converged values of the central displacements are similar for all the analysed HSDTs. Regarding the maximum normal and shear stresses, the differences between the convergence curves for the different HSDTs are almost negligible. When the convergence studies of both laminates are compared, it can be seen that the convergence rate of the stresses is not as dependent on the stacking sequence and the laminate thickness as it is in the case of the convergence of the central displacements. Thus, based on these convergence studies, a regular nodal mesh with $(32+1) \times (32+1)$ nodes achieves similar results when compared with the nodal mesh composed of $(50+1) \times (50+1)$ nodes (having the last one a higher computational cost). Therefore, the first-mentioned mesh was used for further analysis in the next subsections.

2.2. Normalized Maximum Displacements and Stresses. Stress Distribution Across Thickness.

After the definition of the nodal mesh, the bending behaviour of antisymmetric angle-ply laminates subjected to sinusoidal and uniformly distributed loads was studied. In the first study, maximum transverse displacements were obtained using the RPIM and each HSDTs - and also the FSDT - for the laminates $(5/-5)$, $(5/-5)_3$, $(30/-30)$, $(30/-30)_3$, $(45/-45)$ and $(45/-45)_3$ using Material 1. These results are shown in Table 2 for different ratios of the length of the plate over its thickness, a/h . In the same table are also presented the exact analytical solutions for the FSDT and also for Reddy's TSDT, for comparison purposes, since there are no literature solutions for the remaining HSDTs.

The results show a solid agreement with the solutions proposed by Reddy [9], particularly for laminates with a higher number of layers (i.e. lower layer thickness) and a higher ply angle. The less satisfactory results are found for thinner laminates with stacking sequence $(5/-5)$ (this may be related to the nodal density - i.e. a higher number of nodes should decrease the error and approximate the present results to fully converged solutions). The results presented in the mentioned table for Reddy's TSDT were transformed in percentage errors regarding the respective exact solution. The absolute errors are obtained with $\varepsilon(\%) = 100 \times \left| \frac{\xi_{exact} - \xi_{present}}{\xi_{exact}} \right|$, (being ξ a general variable, which can be assumed as the displacement or the stress at a given interest point) and are graphically represented in Fig. 2.

From Fig. 2, it becomes clear that the RPIM is an accurate numerical tool particularly when the laminates with six layers are analyzed where the absolute errors are always inferior to 0.7%.

Proved the accuracy of the RPIM in the determination of the central displacements, the maximum stresses were also obtained, using the laminates $(-45/45)$ and $(-45/45)_4$ with different thicknesses and under two load types. Table 3 shows the obtained RPIM results which, due to a lack of analytical solutions in the literature for this type of laminates analysed with HSDTs, could only be compared with the Navier solution [9] of the FSDT, provided by Reddy using Material 2.

The solutions presented in Table 3 show a good agreement between each other and present also a great agreement with the Navier solution (which used the FSDT, so it cannot be used as a reliable term of comparison with the present solutions using HSDTs). Mantari's theory predicts the highest values for the shear stresses, which may verify the statement made by Mantari: the errors between 3D Elasticity and 2D solutions are lowered in the majority of his calculations when compared with other existing HSDTs. Ambartsumian's theory predicts the lowest shear stresses, this is explained by the fact that this HSDT has the lowest coefficient of the third-order term in the transverse shear function - see part I of this paper. Shi and Reddy's TSDT produce similar solutions since their mathematical representations are formally similar. To prove that the traction boundary conditions are verified for these HSDTs and to verify the smooth stress distributions which are generally obtained with the RPIM, the nondimensionalized normal stress, $\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$, and shear stress, $\bar{\tau}_{xz}$, were computed as a function of the normalized thickness, z/h - Fig. 3. The graphs of Fig. 3 are plotted for laminates with the stacking sequences $(30/-30)$ and $(30/-30)_3$, being the aspect ratio $a/h=10$ for both cases using the elastic properties of Material 1.

From their observation, it can be concluded that the top and bottom boundary conditions are verified (condition of zero shear stresses). Additionally, as expected, the distribution of the normal stresses is discontinuous at layer interfaces (since these results are obtained from constitutive relations) and are non-symmetric. The differences between the curves are almost insignificant in the case of the normal stresses, but when the graphs concerning the transverse shear stresses are observed, it can be seen main differences between the stress distributions computed from each HSDT (with Mantari's

theory predicting the highest maximum shear stress). Regarding the two analysed laminate configurations, it could be verified that, maintaining the ply angles, it is possible to decrease the maximum normal stress by increasing the number of layers.

a/h	Solution	ESL	$\theta = 5^\circ$		$\theta = 30^\circ$		$\theta = 45^\circ$	
			n=1	n=3	n=1	n=3	n=1	n=3
4	Analytical [9]	Reddy	1.2625	1.2282	1.0838	0.8851	1.0203	0.8375
		FSDT	1.3165	1.2647	1.2155	0.8994	1.1576	0.8531
	RPIM	Reddy	1.2719	1.2256	1.0825	0.8812	1.0142	0.8336
		Shi	1.2789	1.2323	1.0870	0.8849	1.0181	0.8371
		Ambartsumian	1.2369	1.1920	1.0592	0.8617	0.9930	0.8149
		Touratier	1.2580	1.2150	1.0629	0.8617	0.9945	0.8265
		Mantari	1.1971	1.1647	0.9850	0.8352	0.9159	0.7864
		FSDT	1.3435	1.2671	1.2245	0.8997	1.1581	0.8533
10	Analytical [9]	Reddy	0.4848	0.4485	0.5916	0.3007	0.5581	0.2745
		FSDT	0.4883	0.4491	0.6099	0.2989	0.5773	0.2728
	RPIM	Reddy	0.5013	0.4496	0.6021	0.2997	0.5552	0.2729
		Shi	0.5178	0.4520	0.6046	0.3010	0.5574	0.2746
		Ambartsumian	0.4403	0.4387	0.5899	0.2938	0.5446	0.2683
		Touratier	0.4979	0.4488	0.5991	0.2994	0.5523	0.2733
		Mantari	0.5157	0.4499	0.5927	0.2995	0.5451	0.2730
		FSDT	0.5254	0.4521	0.6248	0.2992	0.5777	0.2729
20	Analytical [9]	Reddy	0.3579	0.3209	0.5180	0.2127	0.4897	0.1905
		FSDT	0.3586	0.3208	0.5224	0.2121	0.4944	0.1899
	RPIM	Reddy	0.3828	0.3224	0.5307	0.2121	0.4872	0.1898
		Shi	0.3956	0.3242	0.5328	0.2130	0.4891	0.1906
		Ambartsumian	0.3368	0.3149	0.5199	0.2080	0.4779	0.1863
		Touratier	0.3819	0.3222	0.5296	0.2120	0.4862	0.1897
		Mantari	0.3993	0.3264	0.5320	0.2141	0.4878	0.1914
		FSDT	0.3979	0.3240	0.5385	0.2124	0.4947	0.1900
50	Analytical [9]	Reddy	0.3215	0.2842	0.4972	0.1878	0.4704	0.1668
		FSDT	0.3216	0.2841	0.4979	0.1877	0.4712	0.1667
	RPIM	Reddy	0.3438	0.2858	0.5104	0.1873	0.4679	0.1662
		Shi	0.3548	0.2874	0.5124	0.1881	0.4697	0.1668
		Ambartsumian	0.3161	0.2791	0.4999	0.1837	0.4590	0.1631
		Touratier	0.3478	0.2856	0.5099	0.1872	0.4675	0.1661
		Mantari	0.3649	0.2904	0.5144	0.1896	0.4713	0.1681
		FSDT	0.3563	0.2873	0.5141	0.1880	0.4713	0.1667
100	Analytical [9]	Reddy	0.3162	0.2789	0.4942	0.1842	0.4676	0.1634
		FSDT	0.3162	0.2789	0.4944	0.1842	0.4678	0.1633
	RPIM	Reddy	0.3381	0.2805	0.5071	0.1837	0.4648	0.1627
		Shi	0.3413	0.2820	0.5089	0.1845	0.4664	0.1634
		Ambartsumian	0.3105	0.2739	0.4968	0.1801	0.4561	0.1597
		Touratier	0.3374	0.2803	0.5067	0.1836	0.4645	0.1627
		Mantari	0.3399	0.2850	0.5109	0.1860	0.4681	0.1646
		FSDT	0.3419	0.2820	0.5101	0.1844	0.4675	0.1633

Table 2 – Maximum normalized transverse displacements for simply supported antisymmetric angle-ply square laminates subjected to a sinusoidal load (SSL), with the stacking sequence $(\theta / -\theta)_n$.

(a)

(b)

—x— Reddy (5°) —*— Reddy (30°) —Δ— Reddy (45°)

Fig. 2 – Relative errors (%) regarding the respective exact solution for the maximum normalized transverse displacements of a simply supported laminated plate with antisymmetric angle-ply layer, subjected to a sinusoidal load (SSL). (a) $(\theta / -\theta)$ and (a) $(\theta / -\theta)_3$.

2.3. Maximum Central Displacement as Function of the Ply Angle

Using Material 2, maximum nondimensionalized transverse displacements were obtained for antisymmetric angle-ply laminates with different ply angles. Thus, in Fig. 4, graphs were plotted for laminates with a generic stacking sequence

$(-\theta/\theta)_n$ and a specific ratio of the length of the plate over its thickness ($a/h=10$). In Fig. 4, ply angles, θ , are swept between 0° and 90° , and the central displacements are computed for each angle and HSDT using the RPIM.

a/h	Source	ESL	Load	Angle-ply laminate (-45 / 45)				Angle-ply laminate (-45 / 45) ₄				
				$\bar{w} \times 10^2$	$\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$	$\bar{\tau}_{xy}$	$\bar{\tau}_{xz}$	$\bar{w}$	$\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$	$\bar{\tau}_{xy}$	$\bar{\tau}_{xz}$	
10	Analytical	FSDT [9]	SSL	0.8284	0.2498	0.2336	0.2143	0.4198	0.1445	0.1384	0.2487	
			UDL	1.2792	0.3476	0.4274	0.4238	0.6366	0.1957	0.2463	0.4960	
	Reddy [9]	SSL	0.8250	0.2594	0.2029	0.2154	-	-	-	-		
			UDL	1.2361	0.3389	0.4759	0.3796	0.6358	0.2025	0.3017	0.4125	
	RPIM	Reddy	SSL	0.7990	0.2412	0.2496	0.2115	0.4191	0.1490	0.1546	0.2298	
			UDL	1.2361	0.3389	0.4759	0.3796	0.6358	0.2025	0.3017	0.4125	
	(Present)	Shi	SSL	0.8021	0.2417	0.2506	0.2119	0.4208	0.1492	0.1549	0.2302	
			UDL	1.2409	0.3394	0.4791	0.3804	0.6384	0.2027	0.3033	0.4133	
	Ambartsumian	SSL	0.7837	0.2390	0.2346	0.2093	0.4112	0.1480	0.1456	0.2275		
			UDL	1.2111	0.3358	0.4408	0.3700	0.6231	0.2013	0.2775	0.4084	
	Touratier	SSL	0.7949	0.2417	0.2500	0.2155	0.4184	0.1500	0.1556	0.2368		
			UDL	1.2301	0.3394	0.4771	0.3868	0.6350	0.2036	0.3042	0.4248	
	Mantari	SSL	0.7851	0.2442	0.2504	0.2276	0.4170	0.1538	0.1557	0.2617		
			UDL	1.2162	0.3427	0.4767	0.4077	0.6333	0.2081	0.3031	0.4679	
20	Analytical	FSDT [9]	SSL	0.6891	0.2498	0.2336	0.2143	0.2896	0.1445	0.1384	0.2487	
			UDL	1.0907	0.3496	0.4357	0.4305	0.4483	0.1988	0.2550	0.4884	
	RPIM	Reddy	SSL	0.6888	0.2309	0.2391	0.2123	0.2890	0.1366	0.1418	0.2312	
			UDL	1.0767	0.3297	0.4461	0.3793	0.4473	0.1918	0.2673	0.4100	
	(Present)	Shi	SSL	0.6915	0.2314	0.2397	0.2128	0.2902	0.1369	0.1418	0.2316	
			UDL	1.0809	0.3303	0.4476	0.3801	0.4491	0.1921	0.2677	0.4107	
	Ambartsumian	SSL	0.6757	0.2287	0.2287	0.2101	0.2837	0.1356	0.1372	0.2291		
			UDL	1.0554	0.3265	0.4240	0.3753	0.4388	0.1904	0.2566	0.4062	
	Touratier	SSL	0.6875	0.2310	0.2393	0.2166	0.2888	0.1369	0.1421	0.2385		
			UDL	1.0747	0.3298	0.4466	0.3870	0.4470	0.1921	0.2681	0.4230	
	Mantari	SSL	0.6901	0.2327	0.2397	0.2296	0.2911	0.1385	0.1417	0.2655		
			UDL	1.0788	0.3321	0.4470	0.4102	0.4506	0.1941	0.2675	0.4702	
	100	Analytical	FSDT [9]	SSL	0.6564	0.2498	0.2336	0.2143	0.2479	0.1445	0.1384	0.2487
				UDL	1.0305	0.3504	0.4417	0.4188	0.3883	0.2005	0.2630	0.4881
CLPT [9]		SSL	0.6547	0.2498	0.2336	0.2143	0.2462	0.1445	0.1384	0.2487		
			UDL	1.0280	0.3504	0.4421	0.4188	0.3858	0.2006	0.2637	0.4338	
RPIM		Reddy	SSL	0.6527	0.2275	0.2362	0.2089	0.2469	0.1326	0.1381	0.2305	
			UDL	1.0244	0.3267	0.4369	0.3721	0.3867	0.1890	0.2581	0.4057	
(Present)		Shi	SSL	0.6550	0.2279	0.2365	0.2078	0.2479	0.1328	0.1381	0.2302	
			UDL	1.0280	0.3273	0.4375	0.3700	0.3882	0.1893	0.2580	0.4050	
Ambartsumian		SSL	0.6404	0.2253	0.2289	0.2083	0.2424	0.1315	0.1356	0.2284		
			UDL	1.0046	0.3236	0.4218	0.3715	0.3795	0.1875	0.2528	0.4025	
Touratier		SSL	0.6522	0.2274	0.2362	0.2134	0.2468	0.1326	0.1381	0.2380		
			UDL	1.0237	0.3267	0.4369	0.3801	0.3865	0.1890	0.2582	0.4190	
Mantari		SSL	0.6577	0.2287	0.2352	0.2211	0.2498	0.1334	0.1372	0.2626		
			UDL	1.0318	0.3283	0.4345	0.3944	0.3910	0.1901	0.2562	0.4620	

Table 3 – Maximum normalized transverse displacements and stresses in two simply supported antisymmetric angle-ply $(-45 / 45)_n$ square laminates subjected to sinusoidal (SSL) and uniformly distributed loads (UDL). Solutions found with the RPIM.

Fig. 3 – Nodimensionalized normal, $\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$, and shear, $\bar{\tau}_{xz}$, stresses through the thickness of two simply supported antisymmetric square laminates with angle-ply layers subjected to sinusoidal loads (SSL), with aspect ratio $a/h=10$. (a) and (b): $(30^\circ / -30^\circ)$; (c) and (d): $(30^\circ / -30^\circ)_3$.

From Fig. 4(a), it can be concluded that for the laminates with two layers the maximum deflection occurs for ply angles of 17° and 73° , while the minimum deflection occurs for ply angles of 0° or 90° (these angles make the laminate a simple orthotropic plate). For this last configuration (equivalent to an orthotropic plate) a laminate with eight layers (Fig. 4(b)) has its maximum value of deflection, while the minimum deflection is shown for $\theta = 45^\circ$. These observations are valid for Material 2. It can also be stated that the minimum value of the deflection for laminates with two layers is very close to the maximum value for laminates with eight layers. Concerning the HSDTs considered, the presented results do not show significant differences since it is not the purpose of the HSDT to predict with more accuracy the central transverse displacements.

Fig. 4 – Maximum normalized transverse displacements for two simply supported laminated plates with antisymmetric angle-ply layers, (a) $(-\theta/\theta)$ and (b) $(-\theta/\theta)_4$, subjected to a sinusoidal load (SSL). Displacements as a function of the ply angle computed with the RPIM, $a/h=10$.

3. Conclusions

In the problems studied, the HSDTs analysed proved to yield similar solutions in terms of central displacements and maximum normal stresses. Regarding the shear stresses – where the purpose of using HSDTs is found – Mantari’s theory predicts higher values for these components of the stress tensor, which might better approximate the 3D Elasticity solutions than the remaining HSDTs. Reddy and Shi plate models allowed to obtain similar solutions, while Ambartsumian’s theory shown a distinct behaviour, predicting the lower values for the shear stresses than the other two Third-Order Shear Deformation Theories (TSDTs). The present approach ensures the condition of zero shear stresses at the top and bottom boundaries of the plate.

For Reddy’s TSDT (the only HSDT which has documented solutions in the literature), very low errors were achieved with the performed bending analysis, in particular for laminates with plies with 45° orientations of their fibres and with six layers.

In the authors’ opinion, this work successfully extends the field of application of the RPIM – showing its robustness and accuracy – and enhances the state-of-the-art concerning angle-ply laminates for which the literature lacks in providing solutions regarding the bending behaviour of these structures.

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